

ISic1635

I.Sicily inscription 1635

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance

Catacomb Treppiedi A

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645086

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.70

Orsi, P. 1942. Sicilia Bizantina. Tivoli. At 224 no.3

Ferrua, A 1943-1944. Sicilia Bizantina. *Epigraphica*. 5-6: 85-100. At 99

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni giudaica e cristiane di Malta. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 168: 202-208. At 207 fig.3

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